

CARE guidelines for case reports: 13-item checklist

Please indicate in which section each item has been reported in your manuscript. If you feel that an item does not apply to your manuscript, please enter N/A.

For more information about the CARE guidelines, please see <http://www.care-statement.org/>.

No.	Description	Section #
Title		
1	The area of focus and “case report” should appear in the title	Page 1
Keywords		
2	Two to five key words that identify topics covered in this case report	Page 2
Abstract		
3a	Introduction—What is unique about this case? What does it add to the medical literature?	Page 3
3b	The main symptoms of the patient and the important clinical findings	Page 3,4,5
3c	The main diagnoses, therapeutics interventions, and outcomes	Page 4,5
3d	Conclusion—What are the main ‘take-away’ lessons from this case?	Page 6
Introduction		
4	Briefly summarize why this case is unique with medical literature references	Page 6
Patient information		
5a	De-identified demographic information and other patient specific information	Page 3,4
5b	Main concerns and symptoms of the patient	Page 3,4
5c	Medical, family, and psychosocial history including relevant genetic information	Page 3,4
5d	Relevant past interventions and their outcomes	Page 3,4
Clinical findings		
6	Describe the relevant physical examination (PE) and other clinical findings	Page 3,4
Timeline		
7	A timeline of relevant information from the patient’s history and this episode of care	Page 3,4
Diagnostics assessment		
8a	Diagnostic methods (such as PE, laboratory testing, imaging, surveys)	N/A
8b	Diagnostic challenges (such as access, financial, or cultural)	N/A
8c	Diagnostic reasoning including a differential diagnosis	Page 5
8d	Prognostic characteristics (such as staging in oncology) where applicable	N/A
Therapeutic intervention		
9a	Types of intervention (such as pharmacologic, surgical, preventive, self-care)	N/A
9b	Administration of intervention (such as dosage, strength, duration)	N/A
9c	Changes in intervention with rationale	N/A
Follow-up and outcomes		
10a	Clinician and patient-assessed outcomes when appropriate	N/A
10b	Important follow-up diagnostic and other test results	N/A
10c	Intervention adherence and tolerability (how was this assessed?)	N/A
10d	Adverse and unanticipated events	Page 4
Discussion		
11a	Discussion of the strengths and limitations in your approach to this case	Page 5,6
11b	Discussion of the relevant medical literature	Page 5,6
11c	The rationale for conclusions (including assessment of possible causes)	Page 6
11d	The primary “take-away” lessons of this case report	Page 6

Patient perspective

12	When appropriate, the patient can share their perspective on their case	N/A
Informed consent		
13	The patient should give informed consent	Page 7

When submitting your manuscript via the online submission form, please upload the completed checklist as a Figure/supplementary file.

If you would like this checklist to be included alongside your article, we ask that you upload the completed checklist to an online repository and include the guideline type, name of the repository, DOI and license in the *Data availability* section of your manuscript.

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